

European Venom Network Virtual Networking strategy

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Currently, the **European Venom Network** counts more than 170 participants, divided in 5 Working Groups (WGs) and 4 Horizontal Committees (HCs). In the next years, the network will continue to grow, in particular with the addition of International Partner Countries. Moreover, a turnover in the key positions (WG and committees' leaders and co-leaders) is expected. This document has been written to function as a reliable Virtual Networking Strategy and to function as a guide to support virtual activities during the entire lifecycle of the European Venom Network Action. The main scopes are:

- to facilitate fast and effective communication among all the participants, by suggesting and implementing the use of managerial applications and processes
- to facilitate their active participation through the entire lifetime of the Action
- to propose a new set of policies and networking tools in order to comply with the European Commission regulation
- to assure an effective heritage beyond the Action lifecycle.

The strategy has been presented and accepted by the Management Committee on the 02/11/2021 and it includes all the suggestions and improvement that were received. However, this is a living document, and shall be revised and updated yearly.

1. Personal data gathering

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) dictates specific requirements with which businesses must comply to protect the personal data privacy of EU citizens. The regulation also includes the monitoring of data that is exported outside the EU. GDPR is important because it improves the protection of European data subjects' rights and clarifies what companies that process personal data must do to safeguard these rights. All companies and organisations dealing with data from EU citizens must implement the regulations to ensure a secured environment for their customers. Individual consent is at the basis of data storage and transfer. At the same time, individuals have the right to know where the data is being stored and how it is being processed. They also have the right to request corrections or deletion of the stored personal information.

Following these principles, the collection of email and personal information from people that want to register to the Action must comply with the regulation. To comply with GDPR, a **privacy policy**¹ was developed and published on the Action website. The Google form to collect information on the Action members was modified to include the **explicit consent**² to share personal data with the Action. The explicit consent to collect and store personal data, along with a link to the privacy policy, must be provided every time data is collected (online events, registration forms, surveys, etc.). The privacy policy will be revised yearly in order to include any potential change in the EU legislation or to include processes that were not forecasted at the beginning.

2. WGs and HCs communication

Network of researchers are usually based on email communications. This is not amenable for long-term projects such as COST Actions. Documents, decisions and deliverables have to be readily available at any time along the 4 years of the Action lifetime. In addition, deliverables and milestones tracking need to be clearly defined and shared among the Action participants. To allow a smooth transmission of information, three main virtual channels were set up and will be managed during the implementation of the Action:

- A Slack channel including all the Action participants and stakeholders (e.g. amateurs, researchers from other fields, private sector). Slack is a software dedicated to fast communication among projects participants. Thanks to the mobile app, it can be

¹ <https://euven-network.eu/privacy-policy/>

² <https://euven-network.eu/about/#3>

installed on Android/iOS, and function as a reliable tool for fast chat-like communication.

- A dedicated project table in Trello. Trello is an application to track the time and the development stage of a project. WGs leaders and co-leaders will be invited to subscribe and follow the development of their WG deliverables/milestones. In addition, invited subscribers can edit and contribute in a collaborative manner to each project task on Trello, by adding/deleting tasks and documents.
- Document sharing and storage will be done through Dropbox. Dropbox is a cloud-based storage infrastructure that is compliant with GDPR and EU regulation of data security and storage. For each WG and HC, a shared Dropbox folder will be set-up and maintained. The purpose is to store always the last version of the documents related to the WG/HC of relevance. A dedicated folder for Core Team meetings will be also maintained, in which minutes and decision will be always available to the members.

My role as Virtual Networking Manager (VNM) will be to set up and maintain the three channels updated with all the necessary documentation, moderate channels, and assure that all the participants will be equally informed about the Action activities, Grants, events and opportunities.

Despite the online tools are necessary to all the activities related to technology and science, not all the people involved might be used to the utilization of such resources. The strong point of the three suggested applications is that they can easily communicate among each other. In other words, when a document will be uploaded to the dedicated shared Dropbox folder, the link to the document will be uploaded to the dedicated Slack channel, too. If the document is related to a milestone or to a deliverable, it will be also attached to the Trello platform. In this way, whatever application is used, everyone in the Action will be equally informed on the Action progresses.

Email communication will be also maintained. My role as VNM will be to maintain a database of the Action participants emails, roles, and related information. The database will be used to spread news and opportunities from the Action, or related, and to inform all the participants of the Action progresses as well.

To assure the open access to all the materials produced by the Action, an EU-compliant storing strategy is outlined below (chapter 4).

3. STSM Knowledge Transfer

Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSMs) are short transnational visits between COST member states included in the Action. The aim is not only to foster individual mobility of Action members, but also to promote the sharing of all the research infrastructure and methods represented in the Action. STSMs are individual grants. The nature of the grant may result in an individual experience as sole prerogative. To promote the transfer of knowledge from the grantees to the entire Action, an additional requirement to the grantee is introduced here: the “Transfer Knowledge Report” (TKR). An activity report is already a mandatory requirement for every successful STSM grantee. This is, however, a scientific report that attest that the STSM objective has been successfully achieved and it is not shared among the Action members. On the contrary, the TKR is represented by the report of a particular methodology that was part of the STSM (for instance a technique, a protocol, a script, etc.). The TKR will be published by the VNM on a specific section of the website along with the STSM grantee name and contact. In this way, the knowledge of a single STSM can be translated into a heritage for the whole Action. Other people may eventually use the methods, contact the reference person, and upload (by requesting to do so to the VNM) a revised version of the method if needed. The VNM will be in charge to promote the production of such material, ensure its quality, and facilitate the updates.

4. Storage of Action material

Open access is the practice of providing online access to information that is free of charge to the user and is reusable. It is now widely recognised that making research results more accessible to all contributes to better and more efficient science, and to innovation in the public and private sectors. The COST Association supports open access specifically in its funding programmes. Consequently, COST Actions should, whenever possible, freely share knowledge and results for the benefit of the research community and society at large.

As part of the on-line dissemination strategy of the results for the EUVEN, all the documentation produced by the Action must be deposited in ZENODO³. ZENODO is a recognized on-line multi-disciplinary open repository maintained by CERN, and guarantees the full compliance with the data management requirements of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. When the number of uploaded documents will grow, the VNM will evaluate the opportunity to create a ZENODO “community”, i.e. a nested repository within ZENODO that collects all the results coming from the EUVEN Action. All the documents have to

³ <https://zenodo.org>

include, as metadata, the following minimal set of information: *i*) the COST Action full title “European Venom Network”, *ii*) the COST Action number “CA19144”; and *iii*) the acronym “EUVEN”.

5. Events calendar

During the first GP, only few events took place, and mainly in virtual setting, such as conferences and society meetings. Occasionally, Action members have notified some of those events to the Action Chair and the GH manager who took care of disseminating this information by sending an email to the EUVEN mailing list. The Communication team, when informed, was in charge to post the event on social media. Most of the times, the event announcement was directly made through the official social networks of the Action, for instance by tagging EUVEN to Twitter posts. The fragmentary nature of these information, plus the non-uniform way to collect them, may hamper their benefits in favouring knowledge exchange across the network.

With the purpose of collecting and disseminating the information on events that are expected to be interesting for the Action members, a dedicated form was created⁴. This form contains few mandatory questions, in order to collect a minimal set of information for the event that need to be spread thorough the EUVEN network: Event title, Event type, website link, start and end dates. In addition, the submitter can indicate Venue and any additional relevant information. The form will be reachable from the EUVEN website. The VNM will check bimonthly the result of the form and verify the correctness of the submitted information and the appropriateness with the Action scopes, coordinating with the Chair and Vice Chair. The information will be uploaded on the dedicated calendar on the EUVEN website and transmitted to the communication team for a timely and coordinated diffusion of the event.

⁴ Form link:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSe403pjtOMyRpqKDd979Yy2Wsapw6FbrQSarSNUwi_Mx3iIBQ/viewform